

An indicator to map diffuse chemical river pollution considering buffer capacity of riparian vegetation – A pan-European case study on pesticides

Christof J. Weissteiner¹, Alberto Pistocchi^{*}, Dimitar Marinov², Fayçal Bouraoui³, Serenella Sala⁴

Institute for Environment and Sustainability (IES), Joint Research Centre (JRC), European Commission, Via Enrico Fermi, 2749, 21027 Ispra, VA, Italy

HIGHLIGHTS

- QuBES is a new generic indicator for the qualitative assessment of river pollution.
- QuBES allows detection of critical riverside areas in terms of water pollution by pesticides.
- Buffer permeability is modelled according to buffer width and chemical adsorption properties.
- QuBES allows assessment of a specific part of ecosystem services provided by riparian zones.

ARTICLE INFO

Article history:

Received 28 August 2013

Received in revised form 26 February 2014

Accepted 27 February 2014

Available online 29 March 2014

Editor: E.Y. Zeng

Keywords:

Pollution abatement

Diffuse pollution

Chemical river pollution

Riparian buffer

Pesticide

ABSTRACT

Vegetated riparian areas alongside streams are thought to be effective at intercepting and controlling chemical loads from diffuse agricultural sources entering water bodies. Based on a recently compiled European map of riparian zones and a simplified soil chemical balance model, we propose a new indicator at a continental scale. QuBES (Qualitative indicator of Buffered Emissions to Streams) allows a qualitative assessment of European rivers exposed to pesticide input. The indicator consists of normalised pesticide loads to streams computed through a simplified steady-state fate model that distinguishes various chemical groups according to physico-chemical behaviour (solubility and persistence). The retention of pollutants in the buffer zone is modelled according to buffer width and sorption properties. While the indicator may be applied for the study of a generic emission pattern and for a chemical of generic properties, we demonstrate it to the case of agricultural emissions of pesticides. Due to missing geo-spatial data of pesticide emissions, a total pesticide emission scenario is assumed. The QuBES indicator is easy to calculate and requires far less input data and parameterisation than typical chemical-specific models. At the same time, it allows mapping of (i) riparian buffer permeability, (ii) chemical runoff from soils, and (iii) the buffered load of chemicals to the stream network. When the purpose of modelling is limited to identifying chemical pollution patterns and understanding the relative importance of emissions and natural attenuation in soils and stream buffer strips, the indicator may be suggested as a screening level, cost-effective alternative to spatially distributed models of higher complexity.

© 2014 The Authors. Published by Elsevier B.V. This is an open access article under the CC BY license (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/3.0/>).

1. Introduction

Chemical pollution from diffuse sources is identified by the current European legislation as one of the main stressors affecting the quality of rivers (EU, 2000). Most of the time, pollution has been tackled by considering individual substances more or less independently while, in practice, pollution derives from chemical mixtures of many different molecules. As a consequence, while fate and transport models can be run for individual (or a small number of) chemicals to assess environmental concentrations, quantitatively predicting the concentrations of chemical mixtures are not straightforward. It seems unlikely that we can achieve full understanding of chemical pollution through only a

^{*} Corresponding author. Tel.: +39 0332 783658.

E-mail addresses: christof.weissteiner@ext.jrc.ec.europa.eu (C.J. Weissteiner), alberto.pistocchi@jrc.ec.europa.eu (A. Pistocchi), dimitar.marinov@meteo.bg (D. Marinov), faycal.bouraoui@jrc.ec.europa.eu (F. Bouraoui), serenella.sala@jrc.ec.europa.eu (S. Sala).

¹ Tel.: +39 0332 786787.

² Present address: National Institute for Meteorology and Hydrology, Bulgarian Academy of Sciences, 1784 Sofia, 66 Tsarigradsko schausse, Bulgaria. Tel.: +359 2 4624720.

³ Tel.: +39 0332 785173.

⁴ Tel.: +39 0332 786417.

reductionist approach based on the study of individual chemicals. This has shown to generate an endless quest for more data while, for decision support, we are in need of a suitable representation of chemical pollution that makes the problem more manageable.

In addition to the complexity of chemical mixtures, another difficult task is the characterisation of chemical emissions. A direct inventorying of chemical emissions is feasible when a well-defined responsible subject can be identified (e.g. point sources), while a quantification of diffuse sources of contamination can only be made indirectly. For diffuse pollution we adopt the definition of D'Arcy et al. (2000) and Novotny (2003), who define it as pollution arising from land-use activities, dispersed over a catchment and excluding industrial, municipal sewage, deep mine or farm effluent discharge. For diffuse pollution it is often assumed that emissions are distributed according to a pre-defined pattern, e.g. population or agricultural intensity, and are quantified through appropriate "emission factors". For example, pesticide losses are reported to be in the range of 1–5% of the amount applied (Wauchope, 1978; Gaynor et al., 2001). The research question tackled in this paper focuses on the potential to support chemical pollution management by identifying the contamination patterns and priorities of action without referring specifically to individual chemicals and quantitative emission factors, but rather to the typologies of pollutants and the corresponding relevant emission patterns.

We may assume that all chemicals having a certain spatial emission pattern and sharing similar physico-chemical properties will also have similar drivers of their environmental fate. If this assumption holds, then an indicator of the relative intensity of emissions and attenuation processes may suffice to represent chemical risk. This avoids the need to characterise in detail the actual chemical mixtures involved and the fate of individual chemicals based on the specific properties.

Several indicators of chemical risk have been proposed which aim to detect priority areas for action against diffuse pollution. Many examples derive from the assessment of pesticides (Gutsche and Rossberg, 1997; Reus and Leendertse, 2000; e.g. Chen et al., 2002; Padovani et al., 2004; De Zwart, 2005; Schriever and Liess, 2007). Many other indicator approaches rely on geographic information system (GIS) based indicators, such as the attenuation factor of Rao et al. (1985), and have proven useful for decision support e.g. in water resources vulnerability mapping (Bacci, 1993; Corwin et al., 1997; Loague et al., 1998).

In this paper we aim to map diffuse pollution through normalised indicators, derived from simplified fate and transport models, enabling the identification of pollution patterns rather than individual chemicals of concern. We refer to the case of river pollution, and we define a generic indicator for the identification and ranking of areas likely to contribute to the diffuse pollution of streams, taking into account attenuation due to riparian vegetative buffer strips. We call the proposed indicator *Qualitative indicator of Buffered Emissions to Streams* or QuBES.

QuBES surrogates a quantitative estimate of pollutant loads to streams from diffuse sources, by simplifying the mass balance equation of certain categories of chemicals in soils. The presence and the abundance of riparian vegetation alongside streams, which act as pollutant buffer, is specifically considered within this process.

This indicator is intended as a tool to identify potentially critical conditions arising from a combination of relatively high chemical loads coming from the land and a relatively low buffer capacity of riparian ecosystems. Although we demonstrate the approach referring to the case of pesticides, QuBES is intended to be rather general.

After defining the indicator and providing an example application, we discuss its limitations and advantages over more traditional approaches in certain problems of river basin management.

2. Materials and methods

A key point for the assessment of diffuse river pollution is about modelling the environmental fate and transport of the chemicals of

concern, in which the buffering effects of vegetation or structures along the river shores need to be considered. Those effects are acknowledged in the literature (Mander et al., 1997) but only in a few cases (Krysanova et al., 1998; Hattermann et al., 2006) considered in large scale hydrological models.

QuBES is the product of two independent factors representing the two main processes controlling actual contaminant loads to streams: (1) potential contaminant load to streams (Y) and (2) the riparian buffer permeability to pollution (Z), respectively:

$$\text{QuBES} = Y * Z. \quad (1)$$

Term Y [–] is designed to represent the runoff of a pollutant from soil at a given location. The buffer permeability term, Z represents the fraction of the pollutant mass flux from the land that reaches a stream after passing through the riparian zone. Factors Y and Z retain also an individual physical meaning. QuBES as well as Y and Z are all non-dimensional, normalised quantities as discussed in details below.

2.1. Potential contaminant loads (Y)

We assume steady state to compute the mass balance of a generic contaminant in soil, and we further assume (1) concentration equilibrium among the different soil phases and (2) exponential dependence of a chemical's soil degradation rate on temperature. Hence, we can represent the pollutant load L [$\text{kg m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$] to a stream that is potentially generated from the land surface as (Pistocchi, 2014):

$$L \sim E \left(1 + \mu_Q \frac{\lambda Q}{e^{qT} + \alpha'Q + \beta'E_r} + \mu_{E_r} \frac{E_r}{e^{qT} + \alpha'Q + \beta'E_r} \right) \quad (2)$$

where E [$\text{kg m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$] is the pollutant emission to the land surface, Q [m s^{-1}] is the total volumetric water discharge from the land area, of which a fraction λ [–] reaches the stream through the buffer zone, while a fraction $1-\lambda$ infiltrates the shallow aquifer (hence does not contribute directly to the pollution of the nearby stream). E_r [$\text{kg ha}^{-1} \text{yr}^{-1}$] is the soil erosion rate, q is the temperature constant for the degradation rate, μ_Q and μ_{E_r} are constants representing the relative importance of loads through water discharge and erosion compared to direct emissions to water (e.g. by wind drift or dripping to tile drains), while α' and β' represent appropriate constants. A detailed derivation of Eq. (2) is provided in the Supplementary data (S1). Under these assumptions, we may represent pollution loads through a simple combination of emissions (E), landscape and climate drivers (λ , Q, T, E_r) and the physico-chemical properties of pollutants (implicitly included in the other coefficients appearing in the equation). Eq. (2) may be further simplified for different typologies of contaminants as explained in Pistocchi (2014), recalled hereafter.

For non-persistent chemicals, the term $e^{qT} \gg \alpha'Q + \beta'E_r$, hence $e^{qT} + \alpha'Q + \beta'E_r \sim e^{qT}$; very frequently removal through water discharge dominates over removal through erosion (as is the general case for soluble chemicals), i.e. $\mu_Q \gg \mu_{E_r}$, although there may be cases where the contrary is true (hydrophobic chemicals), i.e. $\mu_Q \ll \mu_{E_r}$. So, in the case of non-persistent chemicals, loads can be approximated as:

$$L \sim E \left(1 + \mu_Q \frac{\lambda Q}{e^{qT}} \right) \quad (2a)$$

$$L \sim E \left(1 + \mu_{E_r} \frac{E_r}{e^{qT}} \right) \quad (2b)$$

depending on whether liquid or erosion removal dominates.

In the case of persistent chemicals, $\alpha'Q + \beta'E_r \gg e^{qT}$; additionally, if removal through erosion dominates removal through water discharge

(i.e. $\mu_Q \ll \mu_{E_r}$ and $\alpha'Q \ll \beta'E_r$), loads can be approximated as directly proportional to emissions:

$$L \sim E. \quad (2c)$$

Similarly, when removal through water dominates removal through erosion it may be assumed that:

$$L \sim E(1 + \mu_Q \lambda). \quad (2d)$$

Erosion and water discharge are simultaneous processes although chemicals exhibiting a very strong amphiphilic behaviour (i.e. partitioning equally between a solid and a liquid phase) are not very common. Therefore, it is likely that most situations of practical interest fall within one of the four cases for which load can be predicted using the approximations in Eq. (2a)–(2d), respectively.

The reasoning outlined above enables a number of indicators of chemical load generation from land areas to be defined, which are easily computed using GIS and globally accessible information, as discussed later.

The main problems with Eq. (2a)–(2d) are the terms μ_Q and μ_{E_r} , which depend on both physico-chemical properties of the compound and on management variables, and cannot be given in generic form. For instance, pesticide application techniques that minimise drift or direct losses can lead to the terms in Eq. (2a)–(2d) containing μ_Q and μ_{E_r} significantly exceeding a value of 1. On the contrary, for pesticides applied using traditional equipment and methods, such terms could be significantly less than 1, particularly for less soluble chemicals.

For practical reasons and in order to facilitate the final goal of mapping pesticide loads, we defined four maps (variables), which are summarised in Table 1 (1st part).

Following fuzzy sets theory (Zadeh, 1965), a map of each out of variables X_1 to X_4 in Table 1 can be interpreted as a fuzzy membership function representing how the condition of originating a certain kind of contaminant (see column “Description” in Table 1) is satisfied.

Having introduced this formalism, we may observe that the spatial pattern of a generic chemical load from soil runoff (denoted as Y) can be represented by combinations of variables X_1 to X_4 , as displayed by the formulas in Table 1 (2nd part).

It is worth noting, incidentally, that in the case of persistent non-soluble chemicals, erosion is the dominant mechanism of removal. In this case, it is apparent that loads at steady state are always proportional to emissions and are independent of erosion; however, this is a very unlikely scenario as erosion is typically a slow removal mechanism as long as chemicals are not bound to the very surface of soil and,

comparatively, most chemicals would appear rather “non-persistent”. In addition, there may be cases when it is necessary to consider combinations, other than the four detailed in Table 1, that correspond to the extreme cases of persistence and solubility. For example, for soluble chemicals with moderate persistence and negligible drift (which might sometimes be the case for nutrients), that have removal rates due to degradation comparable to those due to water discharge, Eq. (2) would become:

$$L \sim E \frac{\lambda Q}{e^{\alpha'Q} + \alpha'Q + \beta'E_r} \cong \frac{1}{\frac{e^{\alpha'Q}}{E\lambda Q} + \frac{\alpha'}{E\lambda}} \quad (2)$$

hence the spatial pattern of potential loads can be represented in the form:

$$Y = \frac{X_2 X_4}{X_2 + \alpha' X_4} \quad (3a)$$

where α' assumes now the meaning of an appropriate weight reflecting the relative importance of removal through degradation and water discharge. Parameter α' is specified according to the given physico-chemical properties of the compound. For the purpose of generic chemical mapping, it can be set at $\alpha' = 1$, i.e. the harmonic mean of X_2 and X_4 is taken, which depicts a soluble chemical behaving midway between “persistent” and “non-persistent”. In a similar way, an indicator of load for a non-soluble chemical that is midway between persistent and non-persistent can be estimated by:

$$Y = \frac{X_1 X_3}{X_1 + X_3}. \quad (3b)$$

The combinations of “fundamental” patterns, despite their computational simplicity, require the inclusion of increasing levels of a priori knowledge regarding the relative importance of different transfer mechanisms, and tend to be increasingly specific for certain classes of chemicals.

As previously mentioned, unfortunately, weights μ_Q and μ_{E_r} cannot be specified a priori in a rigorous sense. Nevertheless, expert judgment may be invoked in practical applications by, for example, referring to quantitative estimates of the relative importance of runoff and erosion, compared to direct emissions, for known representative chemicals. These parameters may in practice range from 0.01 to 100 (see Supplementary data S2 for details) and depend on the mode of application of chemicals to the soil. Direct losses from pesticide wind drift can be estimated using some of the available practical methods (e.g. Ganzelmeier

Table 1
1st part: description of variables X_1 to X_4 , each one expressing the (dimensionless) possibility of pesticide loads to streams according to specific pesticide characteristics or environmental situations, and (2nd part) variable combination to create (dimensionless) pesticide loads of distinct characteristics.

Variable	Formula	Description
X_1	norm (E)	Possibility of load to streams due to emission of pesticides which are Persistent and primarily attached to eroded sediments, or any other case when direct emissions outweigh loads through water or erosion
X_2	norm($E \frac{\lambda Q}{\beta'E_r}$)	Non-persistent and primarily solved in water when loads through water outweigh direct emissions
X_3	norm($E \frac{E_r}{\beta'E_r}$)	Non-persistent and primarily attached to eroded sediments when loads through erosion outweigh direct emissions
X_4	norm (λE)	Of load to streams due to emission of persistent and primarily solved in water when loads through water outweigh direct emissions
Combinations of variables X_1 to X_4 to create four distinct types of pesticide loads (Y)		
		<i>Soluble (water advection dominant)</i>
Non-persistent	$Y_{snp} = X_1 + \mu_Q X_2$	<i>Non-soluble (soil advection dominant)</i>
Persistent	$Y_{sp} = X_1 + \mu_Q X_4$	$Y_{nsnp} = X_1 + \mu_{E_r} X_3$
		$Y_{nsp} = X_1$

The norm(–) operator represents linear normalisation, i.e. transformation of a generic map x into a map y , as $y = (x - x_{\min}) / (x_{\max} - x_{\min})$, where x_{\max} and x_{\min} are the maximum and minimum values of map x .

μ_Q and μ_{E_r} : constants representing the relative importance of loads through water discharge λQ (μ_Q), or through erosion E_r (μ_{E_r}) with respect to direct emissions.

Subscripts s, p, n stand for all combinations of soluble, persistent, and “non-”.

Fig. 1. The figure presents the influence of buffer strip width on pesticide load reduction rate. Symbols: reduction rates by edge-of-field buffer strips with conditions of weakly sorption (blue circles) and strongly sorption (red triangles), using the values of Reichenberger et al. (2007), thin lines: the related interpolated curves; thick lines: modelled reduction rates by riparian buffer strips with conditions of weakly sorption (dashed blue) and strongly sorption (continuous red), for the model used (see Formula) a buffer efficiency factor f of 0.75 was assumed.

et al., 1995; Birkved and Hauschild, 2006), while for other less common cases a case-specific judgment may be required.

The terms λ , Q , E_r , and T in Eq. (2a)–(2d) correspond to the landscape and climate drivers of chemical fate and transport, and can be represented in maps. The choice of data required in order to derive such maps is context-dependent, but, for the purpose of pattern identification, rather general and easily accessible data may suffice. The emission map E depends on the chemicals under consideration. When, as in the case of pesticides at European scale discussed below, the spatial distribution of emissions is not known, we may surrogate them with a general pattern of the activities involving the chemicals. In order to represent the emissions of pesticides, we consider as a proxy the intensity of agriculture. This may be expressed by the arable proportion of each 1 km² pixel, derived from the CORINE land cover map for the year 2000 (EC, 2005).

2.2. Stream buffer permeability (Z)

The Y indicator represents potential load generated at a given location, and does not account for the actual amount reaching the stream, which may be strongly influenced by the presence of stream buffers exerting their buffer capacity. Of all the well documented ecological functions of riparian buffers (Naiman et al., 2005) we focus on those most relevant for chemical load reduction, the filtering or buffering functions. As major physical, chemical, and biological fate and transport processes associated with riparian areas, NRC (2002) lists infiltration, deposition, filtration, adsorption, degradation, and assimilation. Most

of these processes are enhanced for increasing retention time within the buffer, which we have assumed to be correlated to the buffer width.

The capacity of a stream buffer of width L_w [m] to reduce loads can be described using an exponential decay model (Baker, 2010):

$$Z = \exp(-f_i L_w) \quad (4)$$

where Z is known as the buffer permeability, and f_i [–] represents the buffer efficiency rate for different land cover types (i).

The buffer efficiency rate f_i may be specified on the basis of land cover type, according to the available literature on this topic (Rohde et al., 1980; Schulz and Peall, 2001; Karthikeyan et al., 2004; Mayer et al., 2005, 2007; Reichenberger et al., 2007).

If buffer permeability, Z , is rescaled between 0 and 1, the ‘load removal or retention capacity’ (or ‘buffer capacity’), for a stream buffer is represented by $B = 1 - Z$. According to the categorisation proposed by Viaud et al. (2004), this indicator is consistent with Haycock and Burt (1993), who defined buffer capacity as the percentage of load input retained or removed. Typically, buffer permeability or buffer capacity (Z or B) should evaluate the abundance of buffering land use classes or the presence of mitigating spatial features (hedges, patches of woodland, wetlands, etc.) that are able to contribute to the abatement of the pollutant by mechanical retention and/or by bio-chemical metabolism. In most cases, suitable land use classes correspond to typical riparian vegetation, comprising semi-natural vegetation such as forest, shrubs, bushes or other vegetation and, more rarely, to wetlands.

In the present work we used a riparian vegetation map covering the European Union, which was recently compiled (Clerici et al., 2011, 2013). The map, available at a spatial resolution of 25 m (reference year 2000), delineates riparian areas on a continuous scale of occurrence probability and was mainly built on hydrological, geomorphological and land use data. The river network corresponds to the Catchment Characterization and Modelling database (CCM2) (Vogt et al., 2003). For the purpose of the present research, the riparian map was modified to also include riparian vegetation (forest/woodland only) located in agricultural areas (Weissteiner et al., 2013).

A pan-European wetland map of similar spatial detail does not presently exist. In the absence of specific data, wetlands according to the level 1 classification from CLC 2000 were combined with riparian areas to provide a consistent representation of buffering elements.

For practical calculations, Z values were downscaled to fit the spatial scale of Y (1 km² grid size). An average per river bank buffer width L_w (single sided buffer) for each 1 km² pixel was calculated by dividing riparian area/km² by river length/km²/2, assuming a symmetric presence of riparian vegetation on both reaches (Weissteiner et al., 2013).

Load reduction rates or functions for buffer strips and wetlands were defined based on the indications from the literature. The physico-chemical properties of the chemical group to be assessed were accounted for by applying distinct load reduction functions and efficiency rates according to the sorption potential, as, expressed by the sorption coefficient K_{oc} (see Supplementary data S3). Fig. 1 and Table 2 summarise the adopted values for the riparian zones and wetlands separately. Background information on the adopted retention values can be found in Supplementary data S4.

3. Example application

We demonstrate the application of QuBES for the analysis of pesticide loads to streams in Europe. Based on EUROSTAT data (2007),

Table 2
Load reduction rates for wetlands (unknown buffer width).

	Constructed wetlands	Natural wetlands
Pesticides transported in sediment phase of run-off	90%, recommended by Reichenberger et al. (2007)	Estimated 100%, due to large buffer width extent for mapped wetlands
Pesticides transported in liquid phase of run-off	60% recommended by Reichenberger et al. (2007)	Estimated 75% due to large buffer width extent for mapped wetlands

Fig. 2. Input maps for the fate model: Proxy for assumed pesticide emissions (equal to arable share, source: CORINE land cover 2000) (A), λ , the fraction of discharge Q that flows into the stream network (source: SUGAR index) (B), runoff (calculated) (C), erosion potential (source: PESERA model) (D) and mean annual temperature (source: CRU climatology) (E). All maps are rescaled to dimensionless relative intensities (0–1).

pesticides applied in the EU for the reporting period 1992–2003 can be described mainly as ‘moderately persistent’ and ‘non-soluble’. For this type of chemicals, an appropriate pattern of loads is the one described by Eq. (3b) above.

For the sake of illustration, we might be interested in evaluating a scenario in which environmental protection policies drive the pesticide market towards increasingly non-persistent and less soluble pesticides. Hence, we can expect a shift from scenarios based on non-soluble and moderately persistent pesticides towards a scenario of non-soluble and non-persistent pesticides for which the appropriate indicator of load is the upper-right entry in Table 1. In order to compute the indicators for the two scenarios, we have to calculate the four variables X_1 to X_4 first, at a European extent.

X_1 , i.e. normalised emissions, were computed by normalising the proportion of arable land per km^2 , calculated on CORINE land cover (Fig. 2). This variable is assumed to represent agricultural intensity and is likely to correlate with emissions of pesticides.

In order to compute X_2 , λ (the fraction of discharge that flows into the stream network) is more difficult to predict and generally requires local estimates based on more or less complex models. Recently, the hydro-geological index SUGAR (SURface water/GroundwATERcontRiBution) has been proposed, derived from a comparison between mapped and potential drainage networks (FOOTPRINT, 2008), which may provide a first indication of λ . SUGAR is reported as classified value ranging between 1 and 10, expressing the probability of that area to contribute to the surface water network. In order to use SUGAR for map algebra the class values have been converted to λ by: $\lambda = (\text{class} - 1) / 9$.

Overall discharge in the form of surface runoff and return flow, Q , has been obtained from the difference between P and ET , where P is

annual precipitation and ET is annual evapotranspiration based on Turc’s formula (Pike, 1964). For the purposes and goals of computing our indicator, the annual climatological mean temperature and total precipitation described by New et al. (2002) were considered sufficient.

X_3 , a measure of the relative intensity of erosion, E_r , was computed by rescaling the map of the Pan-European Soil Erosion Risk Assessment – PESERA (Kirkby et al., 2004), linearly between 0 and $20 \text{ t ha}^{-1} \text{ yr}^{-1}$, and with a constant value of 1 to any erosion value above $20 \text{ t ha}^{-1} \text{ yr}^{-1}$.

X_4 was calculated by normalising the SUGAR index λ multiplied by E_r .

Maps of the parameters used to compute X_1 to X_4 are shown in Fig. 2, while Fig. 3 shows the example maps of indicator Y for three of the four cases outlined in Table 1 corresponding to different types of chemical.

For both scenarios of pesticide loads, buffer permeability (Z) is assumed not to change, as pesticide types in both scenarios have a sorbing behaviour. Indicator Z is depicted in Fig. 4A and B. The buffer permeability provides a distinctive picture for Europe and a zoom on North Italy. The map enables the easy identification of areas with low and high buffer permeabilities. Very low permeabilities are found in wetland areas (e.g. Danube delta, Ireland, German and Danish North Sea coast) and parts of Scandinavia and the Northern Baltic Sea. The highest densities of high buffer permeability are found in Southern Europe but also, to a certain extent, in some Northern and Eastern regions, usually corresponding to areas of high agricultural intensity. High mountain ranges (high relief energy) often show higher buffer permeability than low mountain ranges (less relief energy), which is attributed to geomorphological constraints that sometimes limit the development of riparian areas (e.g. V-shaped valleys). However, this

Fig. 3. Maps of the European study area (A, C, E, G) and North Italy (B, D, F, H) showing the assumed relative loads for various pesticide groups. A, B: pesticides non-soluble and non-persistent; C, D: soluble and non-persistent; E, F: soluble and persistent; G, H: non-soluble and moderate persistent. The colours represent quantiles (20-percentiles, applied to the whole study area) of relative loads, ranging from very low (0+ or lowest quantile) to very high (80+ or highest quantile). Weight $\mu = 10$ applied (relative importance of direct or indirect loads).

Fig. 4. Map of the European study area (A) and North Italy (B) showing the relative buffer permeability, Z, for the group of strongly sorbing pesticides. The colours represent quantiles (20-percentiles, applied to the whole study area) of relative buffer permeability, ranging from very low (0 + or lowest quantile) to very high (80 + or highest quantile).

often becomes irrelevant when combining load and buffer permeability, since typically low load values reduce this effect. The final indicator QuBES, i.e. the product of Y and Z, is depicted for both baseline and future scenario in Fig. 5A and B and Fig. 5C and D. Its value, on a normalised scale, is divided for the ease of interpretation into 5 classes corresponding to quintiles (20-percentiles) of the whole study area, and each class is described in qualitative terms (very high, high, moderate, low, or very low loads reaching the streams). Each quintile contains an equal number of pixels.

QuBES values were found to be highest in certain Mediterranean regions and for intensive agricultural areas in general (including North-European regions). Interestingly, the largest rivers were not always affected as much as their tributaries (e.g. in the case of the Po river). The reason is almost certainly due to the presence of larger riparian widths for the main river, although the exact processes involved would require further investigation. Under the current conditions of moderately persistent non-soluble chemicals, if problems exist they are relatively uniformly spread (see Fig. 5A and B). If we turn to a scenario of non-persistent chemicals, the problem may be more uniformly spread over the region. In this case, landscape and climate drivers tend to play a lesser role, whereas emissions explain most of the variability of loads.

3.1. Discussion

QuBES yields an interpretation of an emission map E in terms of expected loads to the stream network, based on expert-judged environmental behaviour of chemicals (solubility and persistence) and a limited set of driver patterns (X1 to X4, Table 1). As such, it may be applied to rank sites in terms of hazards of stream contamination due to classes of chemicals prior to embarking into a more complex and costly modelling or monitoring exercise. Another use of the indicator is in quick comparison of scenarios in order to understand changes expected in the distribution of problem areas within a region following from modified regulatory or physical (e.g. land use or climate change) conditions. QuBES does not represent changes in loads due to a change in emission patterns and chemical properties, but in the ranking of areas given an emission scenario. For instance, if persistent chemicals are replaced by less persistent ones and emission volumes are reduced, loads will overall decrease; however, due to the different drivers, one area that was ranked low relative to the prior scenario may be ranked higher relative to the posterior scenario. The fact that certain chemicals emitted in a region, due to their known concentrations and toxicities, are or can be

a problem must be ascertained independently before applying the indicator while, once this is acknowledged, QuBES indicates where the problem may be higher or lower.

The mapping example presented above illustrates how an indicator of the expected chemical loads can be defined, according to the intensity of emissions and the relative importance of environmental processes, which are usually related to relatively simple environmental parameters (temperature, erosion, runoff, infiltration). The main factor explaining the distribution of chemical loads to streams is generally the spatial distribution of emissions. However, comparison between Figs. 2 and 5 highlights rather different QuBES values in areas within the same quintile of emissions, depending on the presence of buffer strips. The visual impression delivered by the maps is further corroborated by inspecting the correlation of the QuBES indicator versus its contributing variables (Fig. 7). Highest correlation values are found between QuBES and Z values, which indicate the importance of this variable for the indicator, while it shows that loads cannot be explained by emissions alone, but result from a combination of drivers.

Therefore, QuBES may add to the understanding and ranking of problem areas compared to just each of its contributing layers (including emissions) independently.

The application of QuBES requires elicitation of the weights describing the relative importance of different transfer mechanisms. These must be necessarily assigned by expert judgment in order to reflect the understanding of the chemical behaviour. For instance, for many pesticides it is expected that direct emissions due to drift account for about 0.5% of emissions in Europe (Pistocchi and Bidoglio, personal communication), while runoff may be negligible for certain low-solubility chemicals and dominant for those that are highly soluble. Therefore, a weight of e.g. $\mu_Q = 10$, would be suitable for the latter case, and a lower value of e.g. 0.1, would better suit the former.

The regional pattern of contamination, as reflected by the indicators, can vary considerably from one type of chemicals to another depending on the assumed solubility and persistence. When addressing pollution from a mix of chemicals with different physico-chemical characteristics, one possible use of QuBES is to compute the indicator for a range of types of chemicals and identify areas at risk on the basis of the number of indicators that consistently point to a high risk, or the sum of all normalised indicators.

The soil chemical mass balance (factor Y in QuBES) is based on simplifying assumptions that may bring some errors into the evaluation. The assumption of steady state, for instance, does not allow accounting for the timing of runoff relative to the application of chemicals, which

Fig. 5. Map of the European study area (A, C) and North Italy (B, D) showing the Qualitative indicator of Buffered Emissions to Streams (QuBES) for non-soluble and moderate persistent pesticides (A, B) and for non-soluble and non-persistent pesticides (C, D). The colours represent quantiles (20-percentiles, applied to the whole study area) of relative buffered emissions to rivers, ranging from very low (0 + or lowest quantile) to very high (80 + or highest quantile). Weight $\mu = 1$ applied (relative importance of direct or indirect loads).

may be a key issue (Pistocchi, 2013), and may affect not only the absolute estimation of loads, but also the relative variation across different sites. Another limitation of this model is that hyporheic exchange is not considered. Depending on the type of chemicals and other circumstances (e.g. geological and geomorphological conditions) exchange between river and groundwater may play an important role in determining stream water quality. In particular, a combination of susceptible lowland rivers and persistent/soluble chemicals is prone to this problem.

Also the buffer capacity (B) of a riparian buffer strip depends, apart from buffer width, on a variety of factors including, amongst others, management practices, soil moisture, physico-chemical properties of the substances to be retained, and soil and vegetation characteristics (Daniels and Gilliam, 1996; Reichenberger et al., 2007; Arora et al., 2010). In this study, we accounted only for distinct load reduction functions and efficiency rates according to the sorption potential expressed by the organic carbon–water partition coefficient K_{OC} of the chemical type under assessment.

Another issue with this, as with any other similar indicators or spatial models at the European scale (see e.g. Tiktak et al., 2004), is validation. A proper comparison between QuBES and observed load data is not easy to design due to the need of referring to measurements of chemical loads in buffered streams near agricultural land. Such measurements are simply not generally available. Data might be in principle

available for certain chemicals such as nitrogen and phosphorus but refer primarily to relatively large catchments for which the loading mechanism addressed by QuBES often coexists with other sources of pollution. Similar limitations affect e.g. the pesticide atlas of The Netherlands (De Snoo et al., 2006). The individual components of the indicator rely on relatively well established assumptions: the soil chemical balance underlying factor Y in QuBES is generally acknowledged to be a reasonable first-level approximation (see Pistocchi, 2013), while the attenuation of chemicals in riparian buffer strips (factor Z) is parameterized on the basis of experimental data. However, their combined use should be tested specifically, which is a necessary line of future research. QuBES results should be evaluated using a relatively large area, e.g. at a national or European scale, in order to appreciate its potential for ranking of relative hazards.

It was not possible to identify appropriate datasets of chemical load measurements available for the evaluation of the indicator. QuBES was instead compared with the runoff potential (RP) indicator (Schriever and Liess (2007), Schriever et al. (2007), Kattwinkel et al. (2011)). RP is mapped at European scale by Schriever and Liess (2007), indicating where agricultural activities on non-irrigated arable land can result in high pesticide runoff into adjacent streams, while QuBES aims at describing the spatial patterns of loads of a given group of chemicals, taking into account their fate and transport behaviour, RP focusses more on the potential runoff losses of pesticides described cumulatively

Fig. 6. Scatter plot between QuBES class values and Runoff Potential class values, published by Schriever et al. The graph shows QuBES 20-percentile classes (applied to the whole study area) for non-soluble moderate persistent pesticides and soluble moderate persistent pesticides compared to classes of Runoff Potential on a German test site near Braunschweig. For clarity, overlaying points are slightly displaced.

in a generic way, and focusses more on the presence of emissions near the streams and on rainfall temporal distribution. Schriever et al. (2007) have published measured runoff of pesticides at 20 sites within an agricultural area near Braunschweig, (Germany), which were found to be significantly and positively related to RP.

Fig. 6 shows, for 12 of the 20 sites for which the calculation was possible (the remaining 8 were outside of the stream network assessed in our exercise), a comparison between QuBES for non-soluble and for soluble moderately persistent pesticides, on the abscissa, and RP, on the ordinate. The comparison is made in terms of RP classes (4) as a function of QuBES classes (5). Despite the low number of samples ($n = 12$), correlations between QuBES for non-soluble moderately persistent pesticides ($R = 0.87$) and soluble moderate persistent pesticides ($R = 0.69$) and RP appear significant.

The indicator is not intended (and should not be used) for a detailed analysis and quantitative assessment of loads, but aims at a ranking of the intensity of pesticide loads for the sites of a region. In this sense, QuBES can help identifying hot spots and potential problem areas, which can then be analysed in more detail using more sophisticated models, or considered in the design of exploratory and surveillance monitoring of water quality.

Fig. 7. Correlation coefficient R between two QuBES indicators and their contributing variables.

4. Conclusions

We presented an indicator of chemical loads to streams based on simple soil chemical balance and buffer retention models. The indicator can be easily computed from the accessible maps of chemical fate and the transport drivers and a map of chemical emissions. When emissions are not known, a proxy variable may be considered instead. Chemicals are described as “chemical compounds” rather than individual substances with specific properties: their behaviour is specified qualitatively in terms of solubility, persistence, relative importance of direct and indirect emissions, and the relative importance of removal via degradation and water or sediment advection. This enables the application of the indicator to fuzzy chemical pollution problems such as those entailing mixtures and chemicals not individually well known, including pesticides and drugs applied to soils via sewage sludge or manure. Although, in principle, scale-independent by definition, the indicators of pollutant load (Y), buffer permeability (Z) and QuBES are designed for the prioritisation of potentially polluted sites over large regions. As the indicators are fast to compute, they are particularly suited for the quick assessment of scenarios involving change in emission patterns, fate behaviour of substances, or both. Applied with the necessary caution, they may help decision making regarding required action in the field of river water quality at a regional and global scale. In chemical risk assessment, understanding the causal and spatial relationship between the sources of contamination and exposed organisms and ecosystems have been increasingly shifting from absolute to relative risks, considered fully appropriate for addressing certain policy questions without the need to undertake the difficult endeavour of a comprehensive quantitative assessment under severe data limitations (Landis and Wiegers, 1997; Landis, 2004). In this context, the possibility to quickly interpret a spatial pattern of emissions in terms of the expected chemical loads resulting to streams may improve our understanding of pollution at the regional scale by shifting the focus from the quantitative modelling of specific contaminants (requiring extensive data processing and delivering limited insights when dealing with mixtures and their often uncertain nature) to a semi-quantitative, but more comprehensive, expert reasoning on problem chemical groups (such as pesticides, urban runoff, or veterinary drugs) through the identification of where these chemicals are applied, and which drivers determine their transport. This helps targeting “pollution” as a complex process entailing the transfer of many substances from certain types of sources and via certain drivers, rather than single “pollutants”, in the spirit of relative risk modelling.

Conflict of interest

All authors disclose any actual or potential conflict of interest including any financial, personal or other relationships with other people or organisations within three years of beginning the submitted work that could inappropriately influence, or be perceived to influence, their work.

Acknowledgements

SUGAR data was kindly provided by Igor Dubus from FOOTWAYS (www.footways.eu). The help of Matthias Liess from UFZ Leipzig for providing the geolocation of RP sampling sites is greatly acknowledged.

Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2014.02.124>.

References

- Arora K, Mickelson SK, Helmers MJ, Baker JL. Review of pesticide retention processes occurring in buffer strips receiving agricultural runoff. *J Am Water Res Assoc* 2010; 46:618–47.
- Bacci E. *Ecotoxicology of organic contaminants*. Boca Raton: CRC Press; 1993.
- Baker ME. A strategic planning tool for targeted buffer restoration and enhanced coastal stewardship. NOAA/UNH Cooperative Institute for coastal and estuarine environmental technology (CICEET); 2010. p. 32.
- Birkved M, Hauschild MZ. PestLCA, a model for estimating field emissions of pesticides in agricultural LCA. *Ecological Modelling* 2006;198:433–51.
- Chen P, Hertl P, Chen S, Tierney D. A pesticide surface water mobility index and its relationship with concentrations in agricultural drainage watersheds. *Environ Toxicol Chem* 2002;21:298–308.
- Clerici N, Weissteiner CJ, Paracchini ML, Strobl P. Riparian zones: where green and blue networks meet. Luxembourg: European Community, D. G. Joint Research Centre; 2011. p. 60.
- Clerici N, Weissteiner CJ, Paracchini ML, Boschetti L, Baraldi A, Strobl P. Pan-European distribution modelling of stream riparian zones based on multi-source Earth Observation data. *Ecol Indic* 2013;24:211–23.
- Corwin DL, Vaughan PJ, Loague K. Modeling non-point source pollutants in the vadose zone with GIS. *Environ Sci Tech* 1997;31:2157–75.
- D'Arcy BJ, Ellis JB, Ferrier RC, Jenkins A, Dils R. Diffuse pollution impacts, the environmental and economic impacts of diffuse pollution in the UK; 2000.
- Daniels RB, Gilliam JW. Sediment and chemical load reduction by grass and riparian filters. *Soil Sci Soc Am J* 1996;60:246–51.
- De Snoo GR, Tamis WLM, Vijver MG, Musters C, Van't Zelfde M. Risk mapping of pesticides: the Dutch atlas of pesticide concentrations in surface waters. *Comm. Appl. Biol. Sci.* 71. Ghent University; 2006. p. 49–58. [www.pesticideatlas.nl].
- De Zwart D. Ecological effects of pesticide use in The Netherlands: modeled and observed effects in the field ditch. *Integr Environ Assess Manag* 2005;1:123–34.
- EC. *Image 2000 and CLC 2000 products and methods*. Ispra, Italy: European Commission, Joint Research Centre; 2005.
- EU. Council Directive of 23 October 2002. Establishing a framework for community action in the field of water policy (2000/60/EC). *Off J Eur Communities* 2000;L 327:1–73.
- EUROSTAT. The use of plant protection products in the European Union (2007 Edition), Data 1992–2003. Luxembourg: In: Communities E, editor. Office for Official Publications of the European Communities; 2007. p. 222.
- FOOTPRINT. FOOTPRINT SUGAR, the Surface water/Groundwater contribution index. Produced as part of the EU-funded FOOTPRINT project SSPI-CT-2005-022704; 2008.
- Gaynor JD, Tan CS, Drury CF, Ng HYF, Welacky TW, van Wesenbeck IJ. Tillage, intercrop, and controlled drainage — subirrigation influence atrazine, metribuzin, and metolachlor loss. *J Environ Qual* 2001;30:561–72.
- Ganzelmeier H, Rautmann D, Spangenberg R, Streloke M, Hermann M, Welzelburger HJ. *Studies on the spray drift of plant protection products*. Berlin: Blackwell Wissenschaftsverlag GmbH; 1995.
- Gutsche V, Rossberg D. SYNOPSIS 1.1: a model to assess and to compare the environmental risk potential of active ingredients in plant protection products. *Agr Ecosyst Environ* 1997;64:181–8.
- Hattermann FF, Krysanova V, Habeck A, Bronstert A. Integrating wetlands and riparian zones in river basin modelling. *Ecol Model* 2006;199:379–92.
- Haycock N, Burt T. The sensitivity of rivers to nitrate leaching: the effectiveness of near-streamland as a nutrient retention zone. In: Allison R, Thomas D, editors. *Landscape sensitivity*. London: John Wiley & Sons; 1993. p. 261–72.
- Karthikeyan R, Davis LC, Erickson LE, Al-Khatib K, Kulakow PA, Barnes PL, et al. Potential for plant-based remediation of pesticide-contaminated soil and water using nontarget plants such as trees, shrubs, and grasses. *Taylor & Francis*; 2004. p. 91–101.
- Kattwinkel M, Kuehne J-V, Foit K, Liess M. Climate change, agricultural insecticide exposure, and risk for freshwater communities. *Ecol Appl* 2011;21:2068–81.
- Kirkby MJ, Jones RJA, Irvine B, Gobin A, Govers G, Cerdan O, et al. Pan-European soil erosion risk assessment: the PESERA map, Version 1. In: Bureau ES, editor. Luxembourg: Office for Official Publications of the European Communities; 2004. p. 18.
- Krysanova V, Müller-Wohlfeil D-I, Becker A. Development and test of a spatially distributed hydrological/water quality model for mesoscale watersheds. *Ecol Model* 1998;106: 261–89.
- Landis WG. *Regional scale ecological risk assessment: using the relative risk model*. CRC Press; 2004.
- Landis WG, Wieggers JA. Design considerations and a suggested approach for regional and comparative ecological risk assessment. *Hum Ecol Risk Assess* 1997;3:287–97.
- Loague K, Corwin DL, Ellsworth R. The challenge of predicting non-point source pollution. *Environmental Science and Technology, News and Research Notes*; 1998. p. 130A–3A.
- Mander Ü, Kuusemets V, Lõhmus K, Muring T. Efficiency and dimensioning of riparian buffer zones in agricultural catchments. *Ecol Eng* 1997;8:299–324.
- Mayer PM, Reynolds SKJ, Canfield TJ, McCutchen MD. Riparian buffer width, vegetative cover, and nitrogen removal effectiveness. Cincinnati, Ohio: US-EPA publication. EPA; 2005. p. 27.
- Mayer PM, Reynolds SKJ, McCutchen MD, Canfield TJ. Meta-analysis of nitrogen removal in riparian buffers. *J Environ Qual* 2007;36:1172–80.
- Naiman RJ, Decamps H, McClain M. Riparia — ecology, conservation, and management of streamside communities. Academic Press; 2005.
- NRC Functions and Strategies for Management: Committee on Riparian Zone Functioning and Strategies for Management. Water Science and Technology Board. National Research Council; 2002. p. 449.
- New M, Lister D, Hulme M, Makin I. A high resolution data set of surface climate over global land areas. *Climate Res* 2002;21.
- Novotny V. *Water quality: diffuse pollution and watershed management*. New York: John Wiley and Sons; 2003.
- Padovani L, Trevisan M, Capri E. A calculation procedure to assess potential environmental risk of pesticides at the farm level. *Ecol Indic* 2004;4:111–23.
- Pike JG. The estimation of annual run-off from meteorological data in a tropical climate. *J Hydrol* 1964;2:116–23.
- Pistocchi A. Some considerations on the use of simple box models of contaminant fate in soils. *Environ Monit Assess* 2013;185:2855–67.
- Pistocchi A. Chemical fate and transport indicators and the modeling of contamination patterns. In: Pistocchi A, editor. *GIS Based Chemical Fate Modeling: Principles and Applications*. Wiley; 2014.
- Pistocchi A, Bidoglio G, personal communication. Is it presently possible to assess the spatial distribution of agricultural pesticides in Europe. Unpublished work.
- Rao PSC, Hornsby AG, Jessup RE. Indices for ranking the potential for pesticide contamination of groundwater. *Proc Soil Crop Sci Soc Fla* 1985;44:1–8.
- Reichenberger S, Bach M, Skitschak A, Frede H-G. Mitigation strategies to reduce pesticide inputs into ground- and surface water and their effectiveness: a review. *Sci Total Environ* 2007;384:1–35.
- Reus JAWA, Leendertse PC. The environmental yardstick for pesticides: a practical indicator used in The Netherlands. *Crop Prot* 2000;19:637–41.
- Rohde WA, Asmussen LE, Hauser EW. Trifluralin movement in runoff from a small agricultural watershed. *J Environ Qual* 1980;9:37–42.
- Schriever CA, Liess M. Mapping ecological risk of agricultural pesticide runoff. *Sci Total Environ* 2007;384:264–79.
- Schriever CA, von der Ohe PC, Liess M. Estimating pesticide runoff in small streams. *Chemosphere* 2007;68:2161–71.
- Schulz R, Peall SKC. Effectiveness of a constructed wetland for retention of nonpoint-source pesticide pollution in the Lourens River catchment, South Africa. *Environ Sci Tech* 2001;35:422–6.
- Tiktak A, de Nie DS, Piñeros Garcet JD, Jones A, Vanclooster M. Assessment of the pesticide leaching risk at the Pan-European level. The EuroPEARL approach. *J Hydrol* 2004;289: 222–38.
- Viaud V, Merot P, Baudry J. Hydrochemical buffer assessment in agricultural landscapes: from local to catchment scale. *Environ Manage* 2004;34:559–73.
- Vogt JV, Colombo R, Paracchini ML, de Jager AL, Soille P. CCM River and Catchment Database, Version 1.0. In: J, editor. Report; 2003. [ISBN 20756, Luxembourg].
- Wauchope RD. The pesticide content of surface water draining from agricultural fields — a review. *J Environ Qual* 1978;7:459–72.
- Weissteiner CJ, Bouraoui F, Aloe A. Reduction of nitrogen and phosphorus loads to European rivers by riparian buffer zones. *Knowl Manag Aquat Ecosyst* 2013:08.
- Zadeh LA. Fuzzy sets. *Inf Control* 1965;8:338–53.